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Increasing Awareness of Predatory Academic Practices

RESEARCH ASSESSMENT & OPEN REPOSITORIES II

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Rethinking Research Assessment

Notice please:

1. Research assessment is central to research culture.
2. Overemphasizing quantitative criteria hampers holistic evaluation.
3. Evaluation methods must evolve through experimentation and embracing new ideas.

DORA

The Declaration on
Research Assessment

New Guidance

Guidance on the responsible use of quantitative indicators in research assessment

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New Guidance

Other quantitative indicators t

DORA approach to the use of quantitative information is based on five principles:

Transparent

Ideally, rules for the use of quantitative indicators in research assessment should be developed in dialogue with your research community

Contextual

How will you take account of the proxy and reductive nature inherent in any indicator?

Clear

What is your rationale for using particular quantitative indicators in your research or researcher assessments?

Fair

How will you avoid biases inherent in quantitative indicators? T

Specific

How well does the indicator refer to the qualities of the person or the piece of work being assessed?

The SPACE rubric

A rubric for analyzing
institutional
conditions and
progress indicators

The SPACE rubric

RETHINKING RESEARCH ASSESSMENT

S.P.A.C.E. TO EVOLVE ACADEMIC ASSESSMENT

A RUBRIC FOR ANALYZING INSTITUTIONAL PROGRESS INDICATORS AND CONDITIONS FOR SUCCESS

Research and researcher assessment is a systems challenge, suggesting that institutions that prioritize developing infrastructures to support their efforts may be better positioned to achieve their goals than those focused only on individual solutions.

	FROM FOUNDATION... <i>Core definitions and shared clarity of purpose</i>	TO EXPANSION... <i>Increased traction and capability development</i>	TO SCALING <i>Accelerated uptake and continuous improvement</i>
STANDARDS FOR SCHOLARSHIP <i>How are new definitions of "quality scholarship" formulated and applied?</i>	ALIGNMENT ON VALUES AND GOALS <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> Standards are explicitly designed and articulated to align with institutional mission and values, such as increasing equity and support for traditionally underrepresented, minoritized groups New standards for scholarship consider the balance across research, teaching, and service contributions including training, mentoring and good citizenship Specific definitions and standards of "quality" with regard to scholarship are articulated and shared across disciplines and review/promotion committees	DIVERSIFICATION OF STANDARDS <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> Scholarship is assessed using diverse indicators (e.g. societal impact), units of assessment (e.g. full body of work v. individual articles), and forms of output (e.g. non-journal contributions) Indicators of quality recognize non-individualized activities and accomplishments like team science New definitions of "scholarship" are deployed across the full range of institutional disciplines	ADOPTION OF NEW PRACTICES <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> Faculty have the ability to customize success measures to reflect their research interests and goals New standards, definitions, and criteria for evaluating the quality and impact of scholarship are integrated into the language and processes of new assessment practices
PROCESS MECHANICS AND POLICIES <i>How are new practices incorporated into review structures, processes, and institutional policies?</i>	DEBIASING DELIBERATIVE JUDGMENTS <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> Meaningful and appropriately rigorous qualitative structures for a academic assessment, such as narrative CVs, are given due weight Structures and processes are applied consistently across assessment activities, taking into consideration alternate paths and starting points Use of new assessment mechanics extend beyond traditional evaluative contexts into ensuring equitable opportunities, mentoring, and retention to increase research and researcher diversity	CAPACITY TO SUPPORT NEW ACTIVITIES <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> Training on the goals and procedures of assessment processes and practices are accessible and continually maintained Institutions design processes take into account the resource capacity of committee members to effectively adopt new assessment practices, such as additional burdens on time Institutions have designated senior functions or offices to ensure faculty capacity for new assessment practices and principles	INTEGRATION INTO EXISTING SYSTEMS <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> Assessment mechanics can be flexibly applied and adapted to accommodate diverse disciplines Mechanisms to support practices are codified and written into institutional policies New processes and practices are seamlessly integrated and widely adopted
ACCOUNTABILITY <i>How are individuals and institutions held liable for executing on new assessment practices?</i>	TRANSPARENCY AND CLARITY OF GOALS <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> The goals, principles, and practices of academic assessment and review, promotion, and tenure (RPT) activities are transparent and clearly articulated, and agreed upon by all participants Institutions have clearly defined expectations for adherence to academic assessment practices Examples of "what good looks like" are collected and shared to more concretely illustrate target outcomes and behaviors	ADHERENCE THROUGH COMMITMENT <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> Research evaluators self-monitor adherence to academic assessment principles and practices Senior leaders and committee members actively stipulate equitable assessment practices during both formal and informal career development contexts Institutions model ecosystem-level accountability, such as ensuring that system-level incentives align with and support agreed-upon principles and practices	PROACTIVITY IN ENGAGEMENT <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> Individuals actively contribute to the development and review of new practices and principles Departments proactively broaden and conduct outreach activities to include new or minoritized applicants Faculty serve as "ambassadors" for new academic assessment practices, such as when serving as external committee members
CULTURE WITHIN INSTITUTIONS <i>How are assessment practices perceived and adopted both within and outside of formal evaluation activities?</i>	INCLUSION AND ACCESS <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> More diverse types of individuals are involved in both defining and participating in career advancement processes, such as including early career researchers on RPT committees Representation of minoritized applicants meets or exceeds equity goals for both new hires and researcher retention Career growth and mentoring systems are intentionally designed to provide ongoing support for underrepresented hires	ADVOCACY AT INSTITUTIONAL LEVELS <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> Adoption of new assessment mechanisms is supported and advocated for by departmental and institutional leaders All individuals actively contribute to building more equitable practices—not just minoritized ones New research assessment norms are increasingly adopted as a default by faculty, administrators, and applicants	REFLEXIVITY THROUGH REFLECTION <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> "Positive friction," or intentional pause points to reflect on assessment practices and slow down business-as-usual processes is incorporated into both formal and informal assessment practices All participants in assessment activities feel processes achieve a balance of effectiveness and efficiency
EVALUATIVE AND ITERATIVE FEEDBACK <i>How are intervention outcomes and progress toward institutional values captured and continually improved upon?</i>	ARTICULATION OF DIVERSE INDICATORS <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> Goals and success criteria for individual academic assessment interventions are well-defined and shared Use of leading indicators (e.g. increased diversity of inquiries for open positions) supplements lagging indicators (e.g. increased diversity of hires) when gauging intervention efficacy Goals and success criteria are automatically reviewed whenever institutional strategy is updated	SYSTEMATIZATION TO GAIN CONSISTENCY <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> Quantitative and qualitative data from interventions are captured in a standardized way Mechanisms that capture both quantitative and qualitative feedback are explicitly designed and embedded into assessment processes from the outset Best practices and examples of measurement and/or gathering feedback are codified and shared across disciplines within the institution	IMPROVEMENT USING FEEDBACK LOOPS <i>THIS MIGHT LOOK LIKE...</i> Interventions that don't achieve desired outcomes are considered learning opportunities, not failures Outcomes and data are collected and monitored to ensure high standards of evaluation quality and identify unintended consequences or adverse effects Feedback and other indicators are refined and/or examined in aggregate to identify and investigate patterns or opportunities for course-correction

Debiasing

Debiasing Committee Composition & Deliberative Processes

RETHINKING RESEARCH ASSESSMENT

DEBIASING COMMITTEE COMPOSITION AND DELIBERATIVE PROCESSES

It is generally recognized that more diverse decision-making panels make better decisions: including more perspectives reduces bias, increases transparency, and exposes more individuals to how decisions are made. But old habits die hard, and increasing the diversity of committees demands behavioral change. Here are some strategies that can help.

Diversify across characteristics to support a range of perspectives

While increasing racial and gender representation is critically important, people from other less-represented groups—like first-generation or early career academics, or those with cross-disciplinary experience—can also invite new and valuable perspectives.

Connect committee composition to outcomes through representation of those who will be affected

Deliberately inviting perspectives from those who will be on the receiving end of policy or directly impacted by decisions ensures that issues which might otherwise go unseen have the chance to be addressed.

Transparency invites trust

When decisions about who's included (and who's not) are decided upon behind closed doors, even well-meaning intent can seem mysterious. In contrast, transparent and consistently applied criteria create a baseline and build a foundation of credibility.

Broadening who is exposed to processes can promote equity of opportunity

The ability to see behind the curtain may be especially useful for first-generation researchers or those new to the field. But recognize when committees become a form of added burden in the form of "invisible labor" for those already expected to pull more than their fair share.

Taking a portfolio view

Keeping the bigger picture in mind can protect against the common tendency to make individual decisions, each reasonable in isolation—the so-called "isolated choice effect"—that collectively reinforces familiar norms or standards of decision-making.

Overcome "two-kenism" tendencies

Research indicates that committees stop seeking diversity after selecting two underrepresented individuals, feeling like they've "checked the box." Making diverse representation less like a quota to be filled can also reduce the perception that those individuals must represent entire segments rather than their personal expertise.

Fostering true diversity of opinion

Non-traditional participants may fear judgment or feel a need to check themselves when making suggestions that run counter to established or commonly held views. More inclusive processes deliberately create space to consider all viewpoints, with shared goals in mind.

Relying on self-identification or selection by leadership can reinforce existing biases

Research shows that making selection opt-out rather than opt-in can help boost inclusion of those who less comfortable with self-promotion¹, or those who may not seem like "obvious" choices.

Question the norms about who is qualified to participate or contribute

When traditional or overly narrow forms of inclusion and exclusion—like seniority or rank—are used as criteria too early, they may leave out individuals who can provide important alternative points of view.

Expanding a sense of what's possible

Traditions and historical norms are sticky in part due to status quo bias, but can also persist due to a perceived lack of other alternatives. Gaining exposure to new options by seeing what others have done can help overcome "the way things are done around here."

Debiasing deliberative processes can also reduce "business as usual" decision-making tendencies

Reducing leadership bias

- **Conduct and document "pre-briefs."** Spending time upfront to collectively craft the "rules of the road" for committee work can create alignment and serve as a shared touchpoint that everyone—no matter what their role or seniority—can point to if things go awry.
- **Make all votes count.** Seeing how others are voting can sway where we put our own chips. Techniques like anonymous voting can help reduce tendencies to conform to others' views or confirm safe choices rather than express true preferences.

Reducing individual bias

- **Question what we think we know.** Asking committee members to explicitly step through their thought processes and assumptions can surface and counteract "confirmation bias," or the tendency to prioritize data that reinforces existing preconceptions².
- **Even the playing field.** Consider strategies to reduce advantages of circumstance, providing interview questions in advance can equalize candidates, and using relative measures—such as progress from a starting point rather than judging absolute accomplishments—can gauge applicant quality more fairly.

Increasing systems thinking

- **Identify bias at a system level.** Efforts to reduce personal bias can put the burden on individuals to change, and can ignore how systems themselves are often designed to reinforce "hidden in plain sight" biases.
- **Think downstream.** Improving diversity through hiring will fall flat without equal investment in mentorship and retention.
- **Use structure to provide consistency.** Structured approaches—like interview protocols and pre-determined criteria—can increase confidence in comparison without resorting to solely quantitative measures.

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Schmidt, R. (2022) Rethinking Research Assessment: Debiasing Committee Composition and Processes. DORA

¹ Chang, H., D. Chugh, M. Minnis, and R. Milken (2019) Diversity Thresholds: How Social Norms, Stability and Scarcity Relate to Group Composition. *Academy of Management Journal*, 62, No. 5, 544-571. <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMJ.2017.0440>

² Chang, H., E. Higgins, A. Rai, and R. Milken (2020) The Isolated Choice Effect and Its Implications for Gender Diversity in Organizations. *Management Science*, 66, No. 10, 1000-1010.

³ Ho, J.C., C.K. Kung, and R. Lounsbury (2017) Optimal choice framing attenuates gender differences in the decision to compare in the laboratory and in the field. *PLoS ONE*, 12(12), e0182271. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0182271>

⁴ Cain, M. M., M. Cheng, and M. Pitzer (2014) Invisible Labor: Hidden Work in the Contemporary World. University of California Press.

⁵ Hernandez, J. and S. Precher. Debiasing through the confirmation bias. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology* (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesp.2012.08.010>

Unintended Cognitive and Systems Biases

- 7 personal biases that can influence hiring, promotion, and tenure decisions
- 4 institutional and infrastructural implications of them
- and strategies to develop new institutional conditions that reduce bias.

**Expanding
definitions for
“impact” can help
individuals identify
and embrace
different goals.**

BUILDING BLOCKS FOR IMPACT

Capturing scholarly "impact" often relies on familiar suspects like h-index, JIF, and citations, despite evidence that these indicators are narrow, often misleading, and generally insufficient to capture the full richness of scholarly work. Considering a wider breadth of contributions in assessing the value of academic activities may require a new mental model.

Two dimensions to illustrate "impact"
 Broadening the definition of scholarly "impact" against two dimensions—the scale of contributions' influence and new types of audiences—can help institutions recognize and reward a wider variety of academic achievements and outcomes.

Collaborations, mentoring, and demonstrations of eminence that allow scholars to shape the direction of fields demonstrate increasing scales of impact.

Scale of influence

Scaled magnitude resulting in significant reach, scope, or stature

Collaborative and advisory roles through partnerships and shepherding others' work

Direct contributions through deep disciplinary expertise

Researcher Katalin Karikó's work on mRNA immunogenicity was repeatedly dismissed by elite journals and funders, yet became key to the development of Covid-19 vaccines.

While non-academic works and social media lack the rigor of peer review, communicating the value and importance of scientific advances to wider audiences makes scholarly knowledge more approachable and meaningful.

Recognizing the impact created by cultivating future generations of scholars also rewards contributions of women and minoritized individuals who tend to bear heavier expectations and loads for mentoring.

Open datasets and open science are increasingly valued for their contributions to replication and research transparency. This broadens access and rewards a mindset of collaboration over competition.

New audiences

Reaching audiences outside of disciplinary or academic peers can broaden the societal value derived from scholarly work

Disciplinary or field-specific audiences

Institutions or broader academic settings

Contexts external to academia

Pursue a traditional path
of deep specialization

Applied research, perspectives, and project work provide new forms of visibility and societal value through scholarly activities that directly contribute to real-life challenges.

Emphasize interdisciplinarity,
values collaborations and
foster new capabilities

Recognize efforts that support open research or diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) to enhance their status as critical components of academic values.

Balanced, broad, responsible: A practical guide for research evaluators

Checklist' of 6 practical
suggestions for research funders

Checklist' of 6 practical suggestions for research funders who are seeking to implement or improve responsible assessment of funding applications:

WHY DO WE NEED TO SHIFT RESEARCH EVALUATION?

Research assessment is a central aspect of research culture.

Focusing only on shorthand or quantitative criteria favors a narrow view of research.

The way we assess research needs to move forward through trial and evaluation of new ideas, just like research itself!

A MORE HOLISTIC SYSTEM WILL IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF SCIENCE, AND REQUIRES EXPANDING THE DEFINITION OF RESEARCH OUTPUT, QUALITY, AND IMPACT!

Six practical tips for fostering a more holistic evaluation process

1

Align your decision making to the strategic objectives and specific criteria of the funding institution or funding instrument.

2

Be clear about the context and limitations of any quantitative metrics used and balance them with qualitative parts of the proposal.

3

Look broad instead of narrow to capture the full range of a researcher's contributions, including activities beyond publications and grants.

(e.g. Open Science, teaching and mentoring, service to the research community, societal interaction, and others)

4

Be aware of unintended biases (e.g. Gender, ethnicity, seniority, affiliation, discipline, or others) that arise from scientific and cultural stereotypes.

5

Foster personal and group accountability for responsible research assessment during evaluation.

6

If you are not sure whether you have a conflict of interest or not, ask the funding institution for guidance.

HOW CAN YOU SPREAD THE WORD AND HELP FOSTER A MORE HOLISTIC EVALUATION PROCESS?

The video can be used as a resource in many ways

FUNDERS

- Supporting peer review guidelines and other funding-scheme specific documentation.
- Sharing in communication with evaluators (reviewers and panel members).
- Screening at panel meetings and other group evaluation events.
- Screening at webinars and information sessions for applicants.

INSTITUTIONS

- Supporting institutional checks for research proposals.
- Supporting internal evaluation processes (e.g. recruitment and promotion).

RESEARCHERS

- Preparing grant proposals.
- Peer reviewing work for recruitment, promotion, and grant funding.
- Sharing with your colleagues.

DORA

sfdora.org @DORAssessment

Luxembourg National
Research Fund

www.fnrlu @Fnrlux

SCAN FOR VIDEO

BALANCED, BROAD, RESPONSIBLE

A practical guide for research evaluators

Balanced, Broad, and Responsible

a Practical Guide for Research Evaluators

Balanced, broad, responsible: A practical guide for research evaluators

More Tools developed by DORA:

Resource Library

The Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) recognizes the need to improve the ways in which the outputs of scholarly research are evaluated.

Project TARA:

Project TARA

The Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) recognizes the need to improve the ways in which the outputs of scholarly research are evaluated.

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment

The screenshot shows the homepage of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (COARA). At the top left is the COARA logo, and at the top right is a navigation menu with links for 'About', 'Agreement', 'Coalition', 'News', 'Resources', and 'Contact', along with a 'Sign' button. The main header features the title 'Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment' in large white text on a dark blue background with a digital pattern. Below the title is a paragraph of text: 'Our vision is that the assessment of research, researchers and research organisations recognises the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research. This requires basing assessment primarily on qualitative judgement, for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.' Below this is a section titled 'The Agreement' with a sub-image of a bookshelf. The text under 'The Agreement' reads: 'Based on 10 commitments, establishes a common direction for research assessment reform, while respecting organisations' autonomy. The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment sets a shared direction for changes in assessment practices for research.' Below this is another instance of the 'Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment' title, followed by a paragraph: 'Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (COARA). Our vision is that the assessment of research, researchers and research organisations recognises the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise t...'. At the bottom left of the screenshot is the COARA logo and the text 'CoARA /'.

The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment

Resources

content of research and innovation.

II. Implement the following Commitments:

Core commitments

The core commitments include two commitments to enable better recognition of the diverse practices and activities that maximise the quality of research as well as two commitments to enable a move away from inappropriate uses of metrics.

1. Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research

Purpose: This commitment will broaden recognition of the diverse practices, activities and careers in research, considering the specific nature of research disciplines and other research endeavours.

Scope: Changes in assessment practices should enable recognition of the broad diversity of:

4

3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index

Purpose: This commitment will reduce the dominance of a narrow set of quantitative journal- and publication-based metrics.

Scope: Inappropriate uses of journal- and publication-based metrics in research assessment should be abandoned. In particular, this means moving away from using metrics like the Journal Impact Factor (JIF), Article Influence Score (AIS) and h-index as proxies for quality and impact. 'Inappropriate uses' include:

- relying exclusively on author-based metrics (e.g. counting papers, patents, citations, grants, etc.) to assess quality and/or impact;
- assessing outputs based on metrics relating to publication venue, format or language;
- relying on any other metrics that do not properly capture quality and/or impact.

4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

SCOPE Framework for Research Evaluation

START WITH WHAT YOU VALUE

Begin evaluation by stating your personal values about the subject, avoiding external influences or relying solely on available data sources to prevent the "Streetlight Effect."

CONTEXT CONSIDERATIONS

Consider the context in your evaluation by focusing on the specifics: identify who you are evaluating (considering entity size and discipline) and why you are conducting the evaluation.

OPTIONS FOR EVALUATING

When evaluating, explore both quantitative and qualitative options. Exercise caution when using quantities to represent qualities.

PROBE DEEPLY

In your evaluation, consider potential discrimination, gaming of the approach, unintended consequences, and weigh the cost-benefit.

EVALUATE YOUR EVALUATION

Evaluate your evaluation by assessing whether it achieved its goals, considering both formative and summative aspects. Use SCOPE as a framework for evaluating your evaluation.

Principles of SCOPE

1

Evaluate only where necessary.

The principle emphasizes that evaluation may not always be the most effective strategy. For instance, in cases where the goal is to incentivize certain behaviors, a more productive approach might be to facilitate and enable those behaviors rather than strictly evaluating them. This principle encourages a thoughtful consideration of when and where evaluation is truly essential to achieving the desired outcomes.

2

Evaluate with the evaluated.

This principle underscores the importance of collaboration and inclusivity in the evaluation process. It advocates for a co-design and co-interpretation approach, involving the communities or individuals being evaluated. By including the perspectives and insights of those directly affected, evaluations become more accurate, relevant, and respectful of the diverse experiences and nuances within the evaluated communities.

3

Draw on evaluation expertise.

This principle underscores the necessity of a thorough and informed approach to evaluation, aligning with the standards applied in academic research. It emphasizes the importance of tapping into evaluation expertise to ensure the validity, reliability, and comprehensive understanding of the evaluation process. By incorporating a high level of methodological precision, evaluations become more credible, offering meaningful insights for decision-making and improvement.

METRICS TOOLKIT

Helping you navigate the research metrics landscape

Explore Metrics

Learn more about specific research impact metrics and what they measure.

EXPLORE

- Altmetric Attention Score
- Blog mentions
- Citation percentiles and 'Highly Cited' labels
- Citations, Articles
- Citations, Books and book chapters
- Citations, Data
- Citations, Software
- Downloads, Articles
- Downloads, Books and book chapters
- Downloads, Software
- Field Weighted Citation Impact
- Github: Forks, collaborators, watchers
- Goodreads: Ratings and reviews

- Goodreads: Ratings and reviews
- h-index
- Journal Acceptance Rate
- Journal Impact Factor
- Mendeley Readers
- Monograph holdings
- Monograph sales and rankings
- News Mentions
- Policy mentions
- Publons score
- Pubpeer comments
- Relative Citation Ratio
- Twitter mentions

The background features several stylized orange butterflies of various sizes and orientations, along with some leaf-like shapes. The butterflies are positioned in the top right and bottom right corners, with some appearing to fly towards the center. The overall aesthetic is clean and modern, with a focus on the orange color palette.

Back to repositories

MORE EXAMPLES:

A repository where you can make all of your research outputs available in a citable, shareable and discoverable manner

A CERN Data Centre-backed research data repository for the long-tail of science, enabling researchers to preserve and share their research output from any science, regardless of the size and format.

COAR

Building a sustainable, global knowledge commons

COAR COAR

An international association that brings individual repositories and repository networks together to build capacity, align policies and practices, and act as a global voice for the repository community.

Building a sustainable, global knowledge commons

COAR is an international association that brings together individual repositories and repository networks in order to build capacity, align policies and practices, and act as a global voice for the repository community.

About COAR

COAR

Building a sustainable, global knowledge commons

COAR COAR

COAR Community Groups

COAR Controlled Vocabularies

COAR Notify Initiative

Events and Meetings

Good Practices in Repositories

Multilingual and Non-English Content

Next Generation Repositories

Our Collective Voice

Regional Initiatives and Alignment

BASE (Bielefeld Academic Search Engine): Basic Search

More than 340 mio. scientific documents from more than 11.000 content providers. BASE is one of the...

base-search.net

A search engines for academic web resources. It provides > 340 million documents from > 11,000 content providers.

60% of the indexed documents are OA.

Search 394,013,748 documents from 11,477 content providers

You need to provide info.

BASE is operated by Bielefeld University Library.

CORE – Aggregating the world’s open access research papers

The world’s largest collection of open access research papers

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An open scholarly
infrastructure for
researchers by
researchers

DIRECTORY OF OPEN ACCESS JOURNALS

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Journals Articles

In all fields

80
LANGUAGES

134
COUNTRIES
REPRESENTED

13,563
JOURNALS WITHOUT
FEES

20,457
JOURNALS

10,077,194
ARTICLE RECORDS

FIND OPEN ACCESS JOURNALS & ARTICLES

DOAJ is a unique and extensive index of diverse OA journals from around the world, driven by a growing community, committed to ensuring quality content is freely available online for everyone.

"African intellectuals must do for their languages and cultures what all other intellectuals in history have done for theirs. This is still the challenge of our history. Let's take up the challenge."

Ngugi wa Thiong'O

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Catalogues and links African language resources in order to mitigate the difficulty encountered in discovering African works.

Lanfrica catalogues and links African language resources in order to mitigate the difficulty encountered in discovering African works.

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registries
of

open
access

repositories

OpenDOAR

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Welcome to OpenDOAR

OpenDOAR is the quality-assured, global Directory of Open Access Repositories. You can search and browse through thousands of registered repositories based on a range of features, such as location, software or type of material held. Try it out for yourself:

Repository Name

Welcome to OpenDOAR - Sherpa Services

OpenDOAR is the quality-assured, global Directory of Open Access Repositories. You can search and...

 sherpa.ac.uk

Home About Search Browse

Login | New Entry | Create Account

Welcome to the Registry of Open Access Repositories

The aim of ROAR is to promote the development of open access by providing timely information about the growth and status of repositories throughout the world. Open access to research maximises research access and thereby also research impact, making research more productive and effective. [More information...](#)

Any Country Any Software Any Repository Type Sort by number of reco

Displaying results 1 to 20 of 5603.
1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 | 8 | 9 | 10 | 11 | Next

Export 5603 results as

Search Content Graphical analysis

1. [Networked Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations Union Catalog \(0 records\) - 18 April 2006 \[Record Details\]](#)

SNAS

Sudanese National Academy of Sciences

Increasing Awareness of Predatory Academic Practices

SNAS
Sudanese National Academy of Sciences

Increasing Awareness of Predatory Academic Practices

Increasing Awareness of Predatory Academic Practices

This course is developed to increase researchers and authors awareness of predatory academic practices and to train them on how to avoid being a victim of such practices. It is a project funded by the InterAcademy...

SNAS Sudanese National Academy of Sciences /

“Traveler, there is no path,
The path is made by
walking...”

Antonio Machado

